

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

WAYS OF FORMING THE ENVIRONMENT THAT DETERMINES THE EFFICIENCY OF THE TRAINING PROCESS

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Abstract

The article states that different models (forms) of training provide an adequate learning environment, the existence of this environment is the main factor for students and educators to come together with a common goal, and understanding the set goal as an object of satisfying cognitive needs by the student is necessary for the existence of his continuous - active learning activity. In the research work, the ways of forming the environment that determines the efficiency of the training process are argued, and the interpretation of those ways is given from the scientific-pedagogical and psychological aspects. It is noted that when determining the ways of forming the environment that determines the efficiency of the training process, special attention should be paid to the transformation of the goal of the educator into the goal of the learner, to the realization of the dialectic of whole-part relations in the training system.

Keywords: Educational space, learning environment, learning outcomes, evaluation criteria, SMART planning technique, affective characteristics, emotional intelligence, differentiation and individualization, internal and external motivation, stages of mental development.

Relevance of the research topic. Since education is a value that satisfies the needs of people, it is logical to form it according to the challenges of civilization, and the formation of the educational system according to the requirements of industrial revolutions has taken place in human experience. It is an indisputable fact that at each stage of development of the society, different models of training, perceived as a way of implementing education, have been formed, and these models determine an adequate training environment. The existence of a learning environment is the main factor for students and educators to come together with a common goal, and the understanding of the goal set in this environment as an object of satisfying the cognitive needs of the learner is necessary for the existence of his continuous - active learning activity. The factors determining the direct effectiveness of training are, in fact, focused on the regulation of the training environment, in which the dialectic between the subsystems, parts, and elements contained in the training system (the invariant dependencies between the large system and the small systems it contains and the small systems themselves - effects) is regulated and the system efficiency is increased. We consider the learning environment as a goal-oriented subsystem of the educational space that contains the skills that learners need to acquire. Adjusting the learning environment is a pedagogical problem, and this problem, like many other pedagogical problems, is of a perennial nature. Despite what has been

said, we claim that determining the ways of forming the environment that determines the efficiency of the learning process is an actual pedagogical problem.

Methodological basis of research work. In conducting generalizations on the collected research materials and their scientific interpretation, the "system-structure" dialectical approach based on the "idea of system analysis" (proposed by L.Bertalanfi [5;8]) (the scientific cognitive method developed as a special branch of dialectics [7; 104]) was used as a methodological basis.

Interpretation of generalizations obtained in the study. It is known that the educational space is being formed adequately to the challenges of the IV industrial revolution. In such a place, it is important to find effective ways to implement education on scientific-pedagogical and technological grounds. In fact, at each stage of civilization, the mentioned demand arose, the ways of its satisfaction were sought, and as a result, relevant theories, concepts, paradigms, approaches, and methodical systems were included in the human experience (to say, pedagogical experience, focusing on specificity) as the results of intense scientific research. Currently, in our sovereign country, reforms are being made in the direction of establishing an education system in accordance with the requirements of civilization, and "a legal framework is being established in the direction of citizens receiving quality education".[1]

In our opinion, training, which is perceived as a way of implementing education in a space formed according to the requirements of the modern time, exists in various models (forms), corresponding to the nature of the selected models (forms), an educational environment (training environment) that can be differentiated according to its specific characteristics has been created. The factors that directly or indirectly determine the effectiveness of training are, in fact, focused on the regulation of the training environment, and in this environment, the dialectic between the parts (small systems), subsystems, elements contained in the training system (the invariant dependencies between the large system and the small systems it contains and the small systems themselves - effects) is adjusted and the efficiency of the system is increased. [18; 46] We consider the coming together of learners and educators with a common goal as a determining factor for the existence of a learning environment. The efficiency and successful completion of the training process organized in one form or another directly depends on the effectiveness of the goal, the teacher's goal becoming the perceived goal of the students. Here, it is appropriate to emphasize that the understanding of the goals of training as an object of satisfying the cognitive needs of the learner is necessary for the existence of their continuous and active learning activity over the period of time covered by the organizational form. Naturally, such a question arises: "On what basis and how should the goal considered as a system-creating component be determined?"

The generalizations made on the basis of the analysis of the obtained research materials give reason to say that when the training result is aimed at forming the ability (or abilities) of the learner, the goal is not only the acquisition of knowledge, but the application of knowledge in different contexts. Learning outcomes are key to both learning, teaching and assessment. A well-formed learning outcome should reflect that students will apply the new knowledge and skills they have acquired, not repeat the information. When the teacher determines the goal of the organization of training, "What will I pass?", "What will I teach?" "What will the students learn?" - the approach focused on student activity should be the center of attention. It should not be forgotten that effective learning outcomes describe what is expected of the student, what knowledge and skills will be acquired at the end of the chosen form of organization. [4; 56]

Learning outcomes should be learner-centered, clearly written and understandable, challenging, and at the same time achievable. A clearly explained and learner-centered learning outcome serves as an initial guide to learning something new and increases learners' understanding of content, enabling learners to work confidently and independently.

Scientific sources indicate that SMART planning technique is used during the preparation of training results in modern times. The SMART planning technique focuses on the following requirements: S (specific) - should be specific, that is, training results should be correctly defined and expressed in a precise and clear form; training results indicate what knowledge and skills will be acquired by the end of the organizational

form; M(measurable) - training results must be measurable, that is, the training result must be defined in such a way that the intended knowledge and skills can be evaluated; A(achievable) - attainable, i.e. the set goal should be neither easy nor too difficult to achieve. The goal should be a little harder than the norm, at a level that the student can achieve by working; R(realistic) - real opportunities should be taken into account, that is, training results should be produced in a realistic, reasonable manner, taking into account the available resources and learning environment; T(time-framed) - taking into account a certain time period (as far as possible), that is, a specific time should be set, which indicates the time during which the training results are achieved. Here, it is important to allocate enough time to take the necessary steps to achieve the goal. [4; 57]

It is possible to observe that a number of deficiencies related to the training result were made in the work of practical educators. Among them are the following:

1. Writing an excessive number of training results on one form of organization;
2. Failure to inform the students of the training result;
3. Formulation of the training result in a very complex way;
4. Giving the training result with non-quantifiable verbs (knows, can, sees, etc.);
5. Teacher-centeredness of the learning outcome.

In order to clarify the fourth shortcoming, let us leave a little margin. It is known that what the student will learn as a result of training should be reflected. In this case, the verbs of B. Bloom's taxonomy are used. One of the main functions of Bloom's taxonomy in the learning process is the role in determining the purpose of the organizational form of learning. It is precisely the key verbs of the taxonomy that drive learning in the goal of organizational form. It is not correct to formulate a learning outcome using static verbs that cannot be measured and clearly cannot be evaluated.

Let's not forget that one of the main tasks of the teacher is to achieve the mastery of substandards by students. In order to realize the sub-standards, the teacher determines the learning outcomes that contain the knowledge and skills to be formed in students in each form of organization. Evaluation criteria are derived from those training results. It is logical that the evaluation criteria should correspond to the learning outcomes. Criteria should be measurable, allowing for objective evaluation. For this, it is necessary to use the verbs of Bloom's taxonomy when developing the criteria. These verbs define the levels of learning outcomes and express clear expectations that allow the student's cognitive development to be tracked. Let's also remember that criteria should be shared with students at the beginning of the learning process. Because when students are informed about how they will be evaluated within this process, they approach the process more consciously, they clearly know what is expected of them during their activities.

Among the various ways to ensure the efficiency of the training process, bringing the training closer to the scientific cognitive process is of special importance. Despite what we have said, the learning process is a

complete system and includes steps with a certain logical order, where the analytical and heuristic logics of mental activity unfold as aspects of the unit.

In order to ensure the efficiency of the learning process of students, many scientists-pedagogues and psychologists have conducted research and developed various theories. Among these studies, one of the most effective is the "Conditions of Learning" theory. According to this theory presented by R. Gagne, learning consists of several types and steps. He notes that the effectiveness of learning depends on the proper organization of teaching. According to R. Gagne, how the learner learns is more important than what he learns. It is possible to come to different conclusions when the same topic is presented to different students. Learning is observed through student behavior.

According to R. Gagne, learning is understood as the result of observed behavior. To ensure effective learning, it is important to understand what is happening in the learning process. The main internal factors that affect the learning process are the knowledge, mental skills and cognitive strategies that the student has previously learned. R. Gagne adds to this the affective characteristics of a person. These are our ideas about our interests, views and values. R. Gagne proposed the following steps for the effective organization of the training process, taking into account the conditions of learning: 1) attract students' attention to the lesson; 2) to announce the learning results of the students, 3) to stimulate the knowledge and skills gained from the previous training; 4) to present the topic of the lesson; 5) ensure learning; 6) to ensure application of knowledge and skills; 7) establish feedback; 8) to determine the level of realization of training results; 9) consolidate information and turn it into skills. [4;140] Incidentally, it is not difficult to see that there is a similarity between the steps described here and the stages of the basic organizational form of active/interactive learning.

In our opinion, among the parameters determining the existence of learner-centered training and its efficiency, it is very important that the process in question motivates the activity of the learner.

Psychologist Daniel Goleman divides Emotional Intelligence into five components (self-awareness, self-management, motivation, social awareness, relationship management) in his "Emotional Intelligence" theory. The author of this theory considers motivation to be a component of Emotional Intelligence and one of the factors that motivates a person to achieve. In his opinion, motivation allows to show persistence in difficult situations, especially when things are going smoothly, and finally, to achieve the goal. Motivation is classified as intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. [4; 144-145] By the way, let's note that scientific sources emphasize that the field of motivation has a five-component structure (requirements - meaning of training - motives - goal - emotion and feelings). [3;167]

From a realistic point of view, it is a combination of both internal and external motivation that prompts a person to act. That is, if we separate them completely and say that internal motivation alone is sufficient, it would be wrong. Recent studies show that, on the one hand, internal motivation has a positive effect on the

quality of activity, and on the other hand, external motivation has a positive effect on the quantity. In this regard, both are important together. Motivation is based on two principles: 1) problematic; 2) purposefulness. [2;333] Despite what has been said, if we are looking for ways to create an environment that determines the effectiveness of the training process, we cannot be indifferent to the creation (ensuring the existence) of motivation related to the search for new in the said process.

In order to be motivated to learn, learners need many learning opportunities and opportunities, as well as constant stimulation and support. In this regard, it is important to set up classroom activities effectively and manage the classroom effectively. Learners are involved in the learning process when they see that the teacher loves them in any case, does not judge them, and responds to their needs. An environment in which students can freely express their knowledge and skills is desirable. The learner should be confident that in this class he can always take risks, that is, he can give uncertain answers, conduct experiments, try new things, ask questions, etc.

A supportive learning environment supports diversity within the classroom, enabling all learners to succeed. Strategies to help create an effective learning environment for all may include:

1. Establishing clear minimum standards for behavior;
2. Creating an opportunity for listening to all students;
3. To be aware of the special needs of each student in the class;
4. Providing support in a way that will benefit all students in the class;
5. Enabling learners to choose how to demonstrate their learning;
6. Avoid comparing the development of one student with another (Personal development is key!). [7 ;155]

"Creation of equal opportunities for students" should be guided as an important requirement (principle) for the formation of an effective learning environment for all. Thanks to the expectation of the mentioned principle, the same training conditions are created for the students, and this process becomes possible and regulated thanks to the consideration of their potential capabilities. [10; 62] According to our opinion, the application of "Inquiry and inquiry-based learning", "Project-based learning", "Problem-based learning" models to create equal opportunities for students, due to the application of these models, constructivism and corporatism are drawn into the center of attention, which means interactivity (student-centered learning) conditions.

"Inquiry-based learning" is a model adapted to the teaching process of the scientific method, which reconciles learning with intellectual curiosity. Thus, in the learning process, students are involved in a kind of research activity by asking questions, observing, proposing hypotheses, conducting research, drawing conclusions and checking the results. This activity in itself gives students the opportunity to develop various skills (goal determination, time and priority management, in-

formation processing, teamwork, written and oral communication, criticism, problem solving, evaluation, etc.). [9; 91-96]

The "inquiry and inquiry-based learning" model is a learner-centered approach. Rather than passively receiving information, it involves researching scientific information with the direct participation of the learner. Scientific sources emphasize that "Inquiry and research-based training" can be implemented using the SE model in the educational process. "Inquiry and research-based learning" can be done not only through experiments, but also through research on sources. From this point of view, it is possible to apply the mentioned approach in various subjects. Although Inquiry and inquiry-based learning is a learner-centered learning model, the role and function of the educator is crucial. The occurrence of learning and the correct orientation of the process greatly depends on the teacher's competence and intervention on the spot. The function of the teacher in this process can be described as follows:

- 1) to attract the attention of the students for the introduction to the topic and ask a question that will prompt them to investigate or describe the situation;
- 2) to encourage students to discuss and dialogue about the mentioned question and problem and lead this process;
- 3) to group students according to need or organize a discussion with the whole class;
- 4) carefully monitor discussions and correct misconceptions, and at the same time provide additional information for their better understanding;
- 5) using learners' existing experiences to make learning meaningful.

When summarizing research on "inquiry and inquiry-based learning", its main components as a learning process can be listed as follows: orientation; posing the main question and proposing a hypothesis; investigation; result; discussion.

Among the new directions in didactics, Jeron Bruner's "concept of teaching by making discoveries" is noteworthy. According to this concept, students should understand the world through their own discoveries and acquire knowledge. Such discoveries demand the tension of mental forces from students and have a very effective effect on the development of productive thinking. According to J. Bruner, the sign of creative education is not only the collection and evaluation of knowledge on a certain topic, making relevant generalizations based on it, but also the discovery of regularities that go beyond the scope of the studied material. [14; 22, 20; 53-54]

One of the learner-centered learning models is Project Based Learning (PBL), developed by Goedon, Rogers, Krajczyk, Slavin, Thorp, and Seig. Using "problem-based learning" to help develop cognitive abilities in problem-oriented situations, including "learning how to learn" has gained a well-deserved place in the training practice of recent years. [10; 22]

Since "problem-based learning" is carried out in a group, it inculcates cooperation skills in learners, an environment that includes the unity of constructivism is formed with corporatism (the learning model related to

corporate training was created by D. Johnson and R. Johnson. [8; 467]). [7; 104-106] At the same time, solving any problem and working for it activates their internal motivation and turns learning into a meaningful activity. [17; 210-214]. "Problem-based learning" includes the following stages: presenting an open-ended question that states a problem; clarify the problem, discuss; categorize knowledge (What do we know about the problem? What do we need to know about the problem?); propose possible solutions; share results and solution. At the same time, solving any problem and working for it activates their internal motivation and turns learning into a meaningful activity. [17; 210-214]. "Problem-based learning" includes the following stages: presenting an open-ended question that states a problem; clarify the problem, discuss; categorize knowledge (What do we know about the problem? What do we need to know about the problem?); propose possible solutions; share results and solution. One of the "Learner-centered learning models" is the "Project Based Learning" (PBL) model, in which learners acquire knowledge and skills by conducting research for a certain period of time and searching for answers to more difficult questions and problems. Unlike traditional learning, this learning model does not conclude only with the acquisition of theoretical knowledge, but also involves finding a solution to any problem using theoretical knowledge. "Project-Based Learning" is a model that reconciles knowledge and its application, addressing real-life problems. At the same time, during the process, deepening knowledge experientially, enables the development of skills such as cooperation, communication, and problem solving. [4; 94]

In PBL, finding solutions to difficult and realistic problems is used for students to learn different concepts and principles. The goal here is not to learn and speak knowledge and facts as information, but to ensure that they are able to use this knowledge at the right moment. Project-Based Learning includes the following steps: question (problem formulation; planning; research and product (content, acquired knowledge, skills) preparation); scaffolding (guidance) and monitoring; results verification and process (evaluation of activity).

It should be emphasized that "Project-Based Learning" is not the same as the implementation of projects in various organizational forms of training. In any form of organization, project realization is given to learners after the formation of knowledge and skills for their application, and in "Project Based Learning", knowledge and skills occur during the realization of the project. For example, in the teaching of biology, after studying the internal organs, students make a model of the organ system, but this process is not PBL. "Project-Based Learning" can be applied in the teaching of all subjects. You just need to look at the issues from the perspective of the subject and think about what problem to solve.

As emphasized above, the presented models provoke students to constructive activity. Let's emphasize that constructivism is a theory about the acquisition of new knowledge and ideas through the synthesis, starting from the beginning of the 20th century, J. Piaget, L. Vygotsky, R. Siteyner, M. Montessori, S. Frene, C.

Dewey, D. Kappan, Abdel- Haqq has been put forward by Ismet, Scart-Siter, McKennin and others. [8], [21] According to D. Kappan, constructivism is the process by which learners acquire knowledge by relating it to new ideas or theories that they already have and get from experiences. [6; 2] Constructivism is based on the idea that knowledge is constructed, discovered, created. Implementing constructivist theory requires three things: the active learner, the social learner, and the creative learner. [8;466]

Based on the types of constructivism (a special place is given in scientific sources and these are presented as J. Piaget's psychological [8; 466] and L. Vygotsky's [11; 241-242] social constructivism), this teaching model, starting from the student's initial knowledge and ideas, directs him to the question, prompts the development to respond. Thus, the student actively tries to build new knowledge and skills.

Among the ways of forming the environment that determines the efficiency of the training process, there is also a special place to expect the principle of relevance, to draw attention to the cases where a differential approach and individualization are necessary, to not ignore the ways of thinking of the students, the diversity of intelligence and the gradation of mental development.

The basis of the principle of relevance in training according to the traditional pedagogical system is the requirement to take into account the age characteristics of the students. The principle of relevance requires that the volume and content of the educational material should correspond to the level of intellectual development, existing knowledge, skills and habits of the students. [10; 58]

The content of the principle of the relevance of training is very simple in itself: it implies only the possibilities of learners at different ages - providing them with knowledge at the level of "difficulty within their power". For a long time, as a rule, the level of knowledge, skills and habits given to students in the school experience was determined by "passing measures", and they understood the said principle, which is important in itself, one-sidedly. In the words of some authors (N.M. Boyko, Y.M. Majalite, I.Y. Aleksashina, etc.), they actually interpreted it as "training facilitation" and misunderstood it from a psychological point of view. However, psychological studies clearly show that "as the material is simplified and made easier, the cognitive activity of the students weakens by itself". [3; 47-48]

The formation of the concept of "age capabilities" in psychology and pedagogy was a great achievement of scientific thought. According to L.S. Vygotsky (Lev Vygotsky is a psychologist who emphasized the role and importance of the social factor, i.e., communication and speech in the mental development of a person, and gave a scientific interpretation to the concept of the "Zone of Proximal Development" as one of the most important components of the "Social Development Theory"), "...training to one degree or another should be adapted to the child's level of development - this is an empirically established and repeatedly verified fact. It cannot be denied. A child can be taught literacy only

from a certain age, a child is able to learn algebra only at a certain age. There is probably no need to prove it." [11; 3] The keystone of the principle of relevance has always been important from this point of view, and it is still important now.

Differences of opinion in relation to pedagogical and psychological approaches in scientific sources have existed in all time periods, and this trend is being manifested now. From the science of pedagogy, we know four main concepts (concepts of L.V. Zankov [13], D.V. Elkonin [19], V.V. Davydov [12], A.H. Leontev [15]) related to increasing the developmental function of training. In our opinion, D.V. Elkonin-V.V., which is more popular and applied at all levels of education. Davydov concept. The teaching technology developed by these scientists for all educational structures is fundamentally different in that it gives more priority to the formation of theoretical thinking of schoolchildren. The training carried out in this system significantly raises the theoretical level of education by teaching students not only knowledge and practical skills, but also scientific concepts, artistic images and moral values. In the training system of Elkonin-Davydov, it is recommended to follow two main methodological rules: 1) from the first stage of training, from the day the student comes to school, while teaching these or other things and concepts, theoretical knowledge about their origin and the conditions of their creation should be given; 2) the student should acquire theoretical knowledge gradually and regularly in the process of educational activities. [8; 252] Regarding the principle of relevance, V.V. Davydov states that relevance is contrary to the idea of developmental training due to its practical meaning. [12] However, fundamental theoretical-experimental studies conducted in terms of new pedagogical thinking show that the modern school cannot be satisfied with giving students only knowledge that reaches their abilities. Simplifying the learning material does not inherently solve the problem of mastery. In pedagogical psychology, the principle of developmental training was formed as an alternative to the principle of relevance. In contrast to the principle of relevance, the principle of developmental training implies that training should be structured in such a way that the pace and content of development are controlled legitimately through the organization of instructional influences. [3; 53-54]

As is known, the emergence of the concept of "individualization and differentiation of training" existed as a new stage in the development of the theory and practice of an individual approach. In the theory and practice of training, they were essentially formed as a "training strategy" (Groland) distinguished by its own characteristics and favorable for the emergence of a new pedagogical technology. conditions have been created. [9; 61-62]

The principle of individual approach is implemented in the training process in two ways - through individualization and differentiation of training. The essence of individualization and differentiation of training can only be investigated in the course of training (or education) theory. The main conceptual criteria of individualization and differentiation of training can be ex-

plained only at the junction of developmental and educational training principles. Each student is a unique personality, distinguished by unique individual characteristics. On the one hand, protecting these characteristics, on the other hand, developing them further is considered the main task of the modern school. The individualization and differentiation of education, above all, serves to realize this task. However, there is a second fundamental aspect of this issue: the individual characteristics of students are not the same in terms of educational activity. In this regard, first of all, they distinguish the following characteristics (I. Unt and others): 1) ability to learn (general mental abilities, as well as special abilities); 2) teaching skills; 3) the level of learning, consisting of both curricular and non-curricular knowledge, skills and habits; 4) cognitive interests. According to I. Untun, these indicators are necessary for all students during individualization and differentiation of training. In individual cases, additional indicators, which are more typical for a certain student, can be taken into account. [3;397-398] On the world scale (I.Unt), mainly two forms (or methods) of differentiation are used: 1) at a certain stage, the school separates fields of knowledge, for example, physics, mathematics, etc. branched out on; 2) optional subjects are added to compulsory subjects. At the junction of these forms and methods, different types of schools and classes are created according to the special abilities, interests and professional intentions of the students. [8; 163-164]

Differentiation as a general learning strategy is similar to scaffolding. Thus, the goal in both of them is to achieve the same learning result for different learners, that is, to bring the learner from "where he is" to the target (expected learning result). But at the same time, these two approaches differ from each other. A differential approach is applied to the process covered by the organizational form of training, while scaffolding can cover the entire teaching approach.

The main principle of individualization of training is the principle of enrichment in American psychology and pedagogy. Enrichment of standard programs, which are the same for all students, with new materials according to their individual characteristics, is considered as the main means of individualization of training. They distinguish the following two types: 1) horizontal or lateral; 2) vertical or intensive enrichment. [3;402] Explaining these issues, I. Unt evaluates the in-class individualization of the academic year as a universal form of individualization of training. Determining the content and system of individual assignments is the most relevant theoretical and methodological problem today. In solving this problem, it is of special importance to study the individual characteristics of the students with competence. [9; 60-64]

While arming his students with the necessary knowledge and skills, the teacher who has the emphasis of his art, believes that one day those teenagers, whose role in preparing them for the future life, will use what they have learned. He does not even want to think that a large number of those children will have very little of what they were taught a year or two after leaving school. In many cases, Howard Gardner, who is recog-

nized as the author of the "Multiple intelligence" theory, sees the reason why a small part of the knowledge learned by the student at school is not remembered and used, in the fact that their individuality is not taken into account in the educational process, and everyone is treated the same. It should not be forgotten that people are different, and in this regard, taking into account the differences of students in the learning process, transferring information in different ways allows for more effective learning. H. Gardner shows that first of all, it is important to determine the learning characteristics of students, and then to carry out the process of knowledge transfer by choosing an appropriate activity. From this point of view, knowing the types of intelligence and the characteristic features of each type can be important for teachers, students and all educational workers in general. Even students' awareness of their own intelligence enables self-awareness and increases their metacognitive skills. This also develops students' independent learning skills (the concept of learning to learn).

As a result of his researches, Howard Gardner divided intelligence into 8 (according to some sources 9) types (verbal-linguistic intelligence, logical-mathematical intelligence, musical-rhythmic intelligence, spatial-visual intelligence, naturalistic intelligence, body-kinetic intelligence, interpersonal intelligence, intrapersonal intelligence). classifies. At the same time, he notes that there is no universal list that determines the exact number of human intelligence. Human intelligence is very diverse and colorful. The teacher must identify the intelligence type of each student in the class and use different strategies to ensure their learning. However, this does not mean that in any form of organization, activities should be chosen according to the intelligence of each student. The teacher's combined use of strategies covering different types of intelligence or several working methods makes the learning process effective.

A "theory of multiple mental abilities" is not a "type of theory" that determines which mental ability is appropriate for a person. This is a theory of cognitive functioning, which suggests that each person has abilities in all areas of mental ability. Of course, these 8 types of mental abilities work together in unique ways for each person. Mental abilities always interact with each other. There are several ways to qualify within each category. There is no standard of signs for a person to be considered capable in a specific field. The theory of multiple mental abilities emphasizes the rich variety of ways in which people display their talents within and across mental abilities. [10; 22]

Among the most encountered approaches in modern times is the approach of J. Piaget and L. Vygotsky. Although these scientists' ideas have common aspects, there are also radical differences. While J. Piaget emphasizes that the mental development of children occurs in stages, L. Vygotsky does not accept his approach and states that social relations are the basis of mental development. Contrary to J. Piaget's opinion that "a child's mental development is formed first, then learning takes place", Vygotsky said that "learning is an important, universal aspect of human psychological and cultural development". In other words, learning

comes before development. That is, learning must take place so that development can take place. Like J. Piaget, Vygotsky thought that children's learning takes place mostly during play and stated that language and child development are interdependent because children constantly use language while playing; they discuss roles, express objections to something, correct each other's mistakes, etc., this kind of interaction lays the foundation for knowledge-learning. In this regard, Vygotsky's main contribution was to show us how important the relationships with teachers and peers are in the growth of knowledge and skills of learners. L. Vygotsky formulated this theory, in fact, in response to psychological tests that were widespread at that time. He disagrees with the tendency to analyze children's independent intellectual activities in such tests and stated that they reveal only the mental characteristics that have already been formed in the child, but the functions that are still being formed are left out of these analyses. The Zone of Proximal Development reveals the developing concepts in children. [11; 242-244]

"The main goal of education in school should be to raise a generation that is able to innovate, not repeat what the previous generation did," Jean Piaget's "Theory of the Stages of Mental Development" expressed his opinion, changing the traditional image of the teacher to give information, awakening the interest of research in children, and their own answers to questions. identifies as supporting its finding. He believed that all children go through the same stages in the development of their thinking abilities. What stages of development occur at what specific age can vary from child to child. J. Piaget describes mental development as a qualitative change in thinking and problem-solving skills of children from infancy to adulthood. He identified 4 stages of mental development: sensory-motor; initial action; concrete action; formal practice.

The application of Piaget's theory of mental development in education is the adaptation of training to concrete practical and formal practical stages of development. That is, the content of the training should correspond to the level of development of learning. On the other hand, according to this theory, practical experiences should be included in education for children to learn. Other suggestions include: using visual aids, objects, models; giving students the opportunity to classify and group information according to increasing difficulty, align old knowledge with new knowledge through frameworks and hierarchies; presentation of issues (problems) requiring logical-analytical thinking; create an opportunity to discuss social and cultural issues; teaching broad concepts rather than facts and conveying them within a meaningful context relevant to the learner. [4;126]

Carol Dweck, a psychologist at the Department of Psychology at Stanford University, has shown that some students give up even at the smallest obstacles, while others are more committed to the task at hand. K. Dweck summarized people's view of their own learning and intelligence through two terms: 1) a mindset open to development; 2) a mindset closed to development. Closed-minded students become discouraged when faced with academic difficulties because they think that

either they are not capable or that there is nothing they can do to change the situation. That's why teachers often hear comments from students like "I can't understand this subject" and "It's not me." On the other hand, students with an open mindset do not give up in such situations, instead they change their strategies, ask for help, and turn to additional resources.

K. Dweck determined that students can show better academic performance and results when they are convinced that their character and intelligence are something that can be changed, and how to help students to move from a closed mindset to an open mindset with the right, appropriate intervention and, in general, a growth mindset. how to form a class. For this, the following strategies should be implemented in the classroom: [4;131-133]

First of all, it is necessary to inform students that intelligence is changeable, that nothing is written in stone, and that the brain is flexible.

Another issue is to create a culture of taking risks in the learning process among students. That is, students should not be afraid of making mistakes, they should understand that the path to learning is through mistakes, and they should see their mistakes as a means to reach the goal. Students should be taught that with each new grade, the learning process becomes more complex and the first attempts may not be successful. But you don't need to be afraid of it, you just need to see mistakes as a natural thing and try to make more efforts.

Another thing to consider is using the right kind of praise when praising students. According to the traditional opinion, saying "You are very smart" and "You are a smart kid" to students creates a stimulating effect on them. Recent studies show that such praise prevents students from taking risks because they are afraid of making mistakes and not being seen as intelligent in the eyes of the teacher. This leads them to a closed way of thinking. Therefore, when praising students, teachers should not praise their intelligence and mind, but their hard work, their efforts, their involvement in the process, the strategies, methods and ways they use. Knowing that intelligence is a variable characteristic allows both teachers and students to properly structure the learning process, create an appropriate learning environment in the classroom, and enjoy learning.

The result. 1. Two important conditions should be kept in focus when determining the ways of forming the environment that determines the efficiency of the training process: 1) the goal adopted by the teacher in the training process (the behavioral model that will become the expected result) should become the goal of the learner, (that is, the learning result that is planned to be mastered should become the object of satisfying the cognitive needs of the learner, in this case the learning process can become a "learner-centered process"); 2) the dialectic of whole-part relations must be realized in the educational system.

2. In the training process, importance should be given to the following ideas and appropriate strategies: 1) students' motivation to learn; 2) understanding by students that intellect, intelligence is changeable, the

brain is flexible; 3) the expectation of the principle of relevance, drawing attention to the cases where a differential approach and individualization are necessary, not ignoring the ways of thinking of the students, the diversity of intelligence and the gradation of mental development; 4) the teacher's combined use of strategies covering different types of intelligence or several working methods; 5) being guided by the important principle of creating equal opportunities for students for the formation of an effective learning environment for all.

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